

D3.3 – Analysis of the business strategy for the sustainability of the OITB

WP3 – Test Line upgrade & Long Term business strategy

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Goal and scope of the deliverable

This document is the first release of the Deliverable 3.3, pertaining to the activities developed by the Task 3.3. This task is aimed at developing a Business Plan and Strategy for the Open Innovation Test Bed (OITB) and validating it by confirming its financial, operational, environmental sustainability, and strategic relevance for the involved players.

This document represents a first release in the sense that the main economic and financial parameters of the business and of the projections will be then updated throughout the evolution of the project. In fact, the business model of the H₂SHIFT project will be rooted in a solid Business Plan that will prove the economical sustainability and profitability of the OITB – through the Single Entry Point (SEP) – soon after the 4-year co-funded project period. The overall business Plan and Strategy of the OITB is shaped based on the business information of each test line (TL).

The scope of the first release of deliverable D3.3 is to provide the general structure of the Business Plan. The goals of the document are to present the general content of the OITB Business Plan and to identify the relevant information that are required to formulate the Plan and the Strategy for the project.

The final Business Plan and Strategy will be elaborated based on this starting structure throughout the project and progressively updated when all the required information will be available, to be released at the end of the project (Deliverable due at M45) in the form of a public document. Most of the information that are required for the elaboration of the business plan that are listed in the present document are confidential, and will be elaborated and presented in aggregated form in the final deliverable.

1 Business Plan: general structure

The Business Plan will harmonize the general vision and objectives of the project with the specific business information from the TL owners. To prepare a comprehensive and effective business plan for the project, various types of information will be gathered from the SEP management and the owners of the TLs to ensure that all aspects of the business are included.

The Business Plan will include the following key information:

1. OITB concept and objectives
 - General overview of H₂SHIFT vision and objectives
 - Overview of TLs owner companies: vision, mission and core values
 - Business objectives of the TLs owner companies: short- and long-term objectives related to the OITB, during the project and after.
2. Market analysis
 - Target Market and Customer Needs: description of the OITB target customers of the project and analysis of user needs for the TLs, including results of deliverable D3.2 and its updates.
 - Market Size and Trends: TL users demand, estimation of growth potential.
 - Competitive Analysis: information on similar infrastructures offered worldwide.
 - Regulatory Environment: hydrogen regulation environment in EU, including results of deliverable D3.1.
3. Business Model and marketing strategy
 - OITB Services: summary of the offerings, unique value propositions, and benefits for each TL.
 - Pricing Strategy: How services of each TL will be priced and the rationale behind it.
 - OITB access: description of the mechanism of access to the SEP through open calls.
 - Revenue Streams: How the business will generate income, for the SEP and for each TL.
 - Marketing Strategy and Sales Plan: general strategy within the project to promote the access to the OITB and planning to promote the access after the end of the project.
 - Customer acquisition costs: cost of promoting the OITB and engaging new customers.
 - Customer retention strategies: strategy for keeping customers engaged.
4. Operations Plan and organizational structure of the TLs
 - Organizational information of the TLs: staff involved, roles and responsibilities for the TL management during the project and afterwards.
 - Facilities, Equipment and Technology Requirements: summary of technical information about TLs, with reference to the results from Task 3.4. (Test Line upgrade analysis – D3.4).
 - Supply Chain Management: information about each TL inventory management (i.e. spare parts and consumables) processes.
 - Operational Workflow: Key processes in production, service delivery, and logistics. Includes information on operative safety and security protocols applied in the TL for testing and data handling (i.e. IPR protection).
5. Financial Plan
 - Test line Costs: investment required for upgrading/maintenance of the current infrastructure.
 - Revenue Projections: TL accesses forecasts for the next 3-5 years after the project.
 - Expense Projections: operating costs (materials and personnel) and marketing costs.
 - Profit and Loss Statement: Expected income and profitability.
 - Cash Flow Statement: Projections of inflows and outflows.

- Break-even Analysis: The point at which the business will become profitable.
 - Funding Requirements and use: possible future funding needs and how the funds will be used.
6. Risk Assessment
- SWOT Analysis: Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats.
 - Risk Mitigation Strategies: Plans to address potential risks.
 - Contingency Plans: Backup plans for critical operations.

The contents of the sections and the information that will be provided by the SEP management and TL owners are summarized in the following parts of the document.

2 Business Plan details

2.1 OITB concept and objectives

This section of the plan provides general background information in terms of business objectives. In this part, the general overview of the H₂SHIFT project is described, with its objectives (section already developed and included in the present document) and the specific description and objectives of the partners owners of the TLs.

2.1.1 General overview of H₂SHIFT vision and objectives

H₂SHIFT concept

The H₂SHIFT project employs a multi-stakeholder, user-focused approach to establish the Open Innovation Test Bed (OITB), fostering value creation and capture across a diverse range of stakeholders. The initiative provides access to nine Test Lines (seven technical and two non-technical) covering a broad spectrum of hydrogen production technologies. These Test Lines offer services for testing, technology upscaling, and non-technical support through academic and industrial partners with extensive expertise in hydrogen production. The objective is to assist companies, particularly startups and SMEs, in scaling up their technologies.

A Single Entry Point (SEP) serves as a centralized hub for companies to access these services. Acting as a streamlined gateway, the SEP collects, analyzes, and directs requests to the most suitable testing services, with the goal of fostering the development, testing, and adoption of innovative, high-performance, safe, and eco-friendly hydrogen production technologies. Starting in the third year of the project, dedicated Open Calls (OCs) will provide access to the OITB, with up to 12 projects (referred to as "democases") being selected to validate the OITB's operations, accessibility, and sustainability. This will support the EU's industrial transformation and energy transition goals.

Business Concept

The project's business model revolves around four key elements:

- **Customers:** Innovative startups and SMEs globally, benefitting from a comprehensive support package that includes state-of-the-art facilities, expert services, and unmatched technical expertise to advance their hydrogen production technologies. These technologies will progress from Proof of Concept (TRL 3) and laboratory validation (TRL 4) to prototype demonstration in industrial settings (TRL 7/8).
- **Value Chain:** A cohesive ecosystem that links research institutions, academia, industry, and investors, leveraging unrivaled resources and capabilities through technical services, process upscaling, and non-technical support.
- **Value Proposition:** Accelerating the deployment of cutting-edge hydrogen production technologies in alignment with the Clean Hydrogen Joint Undertaking Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (Clean H₂ JU SRIA), facilitated by an effective and sustainable OITB model.
- **Profit Mechanism:** A scalable pay-per-use system reduces the financial barriers for startups and SMEs to access advanced facilities. Additional revenue streams include the sale of hydrogen and biogenic carbon dioxide.

Revenue and Sustainability Model

The H₂SHIFT model aims to achieve OITB profitability shortly after the four-year co-funded project period. Each Test Line will contribute to the SEP's creation and management costs through a membership fee. This fee consists of a fixed portion for initial setup costs and a variable portion based on a percentage of Test Line-generated revenues.

Revenue streams include:

- Hydrogen Production Test Lines:
 - Access fees for OITB testing facilities.
 - Sales of hydrogen produced and stored during tests.
 - Sales of biogenic carbon dioxide captured during tests.
- Non-Technical Test Lines:
 - Service fees paid by users.

During the project's initial four years, consortium members can access OITB services free of charge. Selected startups and SMEs participating via Open Calls will pay fair and reasonable access fees to cover unfunded costs. Transparent pricing, security, safety, and intellectual property rights will be upheld in all agreements. EU funding is crucial for achieving the critical scale of technologies and companies within the newly created ecosystem.

From the fifth year onward, the SEP will continue managing the OITB, making its facilities and services accessible to all interested parties—both within and beyond Europe—on fair terms and pricing. Access will no longer be restricted to consortium members or Open Call participants. The OITB will enlarge the services offered following the evolution of the demand, eventually adding other Test Lines. All contractual agreements with the SEP will clearly define the resources and services provided.

2.1.2 OITB: vision, mission and core values

Information about OITB vision, mission and core values concerning the services offered within the project.

Vision Statement

- What is long-term vision of the OITB about the research & development services provided in the field of hydrogen production?
- How does the OITB aspire to impact the TL customers, and in general the hydrogen value chain and society?

Mission Statement

- What is the mission of the OITB in the field of hydrogen research & development, in particular with reference to the services offered?
- Who are the OITB primary Test Line customers, and what value does it deliver to them?

Core Values

- What are the guiding principles that drive the decisions and culture?
- How do these values reflect the approach to business, employees, and stakeholders?

2.1.3 Business objectives of the OITB: short- and long-term objectives, during the project and after.

This section gathers insights into strategic aspirations concerning the services offered in the OITB.

Short-Term Goals (within H₂SHIFT project)

- What are the OITB goals within H₂SHIFT?
- How does the OITB plan to achieve these goals?
- What are the specific targets and KPIs related to infrastructure growth (i.e., upgrades and enlargement of the offer) and accesses to the infrastructure during the project?
- Are there any specific projects, partnerships, or initiatives currently in progress that will contribute to develop the TL infrastructure and related services synergically with H₂SHIFT project?

Long-Term Goals (after the project)

- What are broader objectives for the future concerning the services offered in the OITB?
- How does the OITB intend to scale its operations or expand?
- What strategies are in place to ensure sustainability and adaptability for the future?
- Are there any innovation or diversification plans in the pipeline?

2.2 Market analysis

This section of the plan provides the information about the market for the OITB, which is represented by the potential customers of the infrastructure.

2.2.1 Target Market and Customer Needs

This section includes the description and the analysis of the OITB target customers of the project. The section will highlight how the OITB services will solve SMEs' difficulties in accessing high-end hydrogen testing and upscaling facilities at reasonable costs. Content will include:

- **Target market:** Description of the target users, the potential customers of the OITB, including inputs from WP2 (Ecosystem Mapping) and WP6 (Exploitation).
- **Customer needs and expectations:** Summary of the analysis of users' needs, from deliverable D3.2. The survey performed in D3.2 will be extended during the project to increase the number of respondents and the updated results will be summarized in this section of the Business Plan.
- **"Pain Points":** Specific challenges customers experience (e.g., high costs, inefficiency, lack of scalability).
- **Service access behavior:** How, when, and why customers purchase similar products or services.

2.2.2 Market Size and Trends

This section will quantify: 1) the direct customer market for the OITB services (i.e., SMEs, startups), highlighting its potential, and 2) the market for hydrogen and CO₂ (trend analysis and price scenarios), as possible additional revenue sources. Content includes:

- **Market Size:** Current numbers of companies, in particular SMEs and startups, active in the hydrogen value chain in EU and worldwide, and estimated growth rates. Hydrogen and CO₂ market.
- **Trends:** Summary of emerging opportunities in the hydrogen production sector and technological advances that could impact the OITB with the introduction of additional Test Lines. Trend analysis and price scenarios for hydrogen and CO₂.
- **Data Sources:** Summary of references (e.g., ecosystem map (WP2), industry reports, government publications, and trade associations, etc.).

2.2.3 Competitive Analysis

A thorough examination of the OITB competition to highlight the unique advantages. Content Includes:

- **Direct Competitors:** Companies offering similar products or services.
- **Indirect Competitors:** Alternatives customers might choose instead.
- **Market Share Analysis:** Who dominates the market of the different services offered by the OITB, and why. The analysis will include their geographical reach, the range of services offered, any technological or operational advantages, and if available their pricing strategies.
- **Benchmarking** of the H₂SHIFT solution with other leading global hydrogen test beds worldwide (e.g. CleanHyPro project).
- **SWOT Analysis:** Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats for competitors and OITB.

2.2.4 Regulatory Environment

Details of the EU and worldwide regulations promoting hydrogen research and development and how the OITB services offered align with these regulations giving the H₂SHIFT services a competitive edge. Content includes:

- **Key Regulations:** Relevant laws, standards, and certifications. Summary of findings from deliverable D3.1.
- **Compliance Requirements:** standards that Test Lines must comply to offer standardized services to the potential customers.
- **Opportunities and Barriers:** Regulations that could help or hinder customers access to the services or expansion of the services offered.

The different subsections will be organized in a PESTEL Analysis (Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, Legal), to highlight the key external forces that could affect the business outcomes for the project

2.3 Business Model and marketing strategy

This section includes the information about the services offered, the mechanism to access the services, the pricing strategy and revenue streams obtained, and the marketing strategy to promote the access to the OITB.

2.3.1 OITB Services description

Detailed description of the experimental and non-technical services offered, highlighting their unique value. Content includes, for each Test Line:

- **Technical Services:** description of the cutting-edge hydrogen production experimental test facilities for technology validation, scaling, and performance optimization.
- **Non-Technical Services:** description of the non-technical services offered. The service provides under this category are: technology upscaling services (prototyping for industrial scalability and computational modeling), and consultancy services. The consultancy services will cover the following areas:
 - *Techno-Economic Assessment:* it involves evaluating the economic viability and feasibility of a technology or project. It looks at factors such as capital costs, operational costs, revenue generation, and potential return on investment. The goal is to help companies understand the financial implications of adopting or upscaling a particular technology.
 - *Life Cycle Assessment (LCA):* LCA is a comprehensive analysis of the environmental impact of a product or process throughout its entire life cycle, from raw material extraction to production, use, and disposal. It assesses factors like resource consumption, emissions, and waste generation. The aim is to provide insights into the environmental sustainability of a technology.
 - *Legal Requirements:* it involves identifying and understanding the legal obligations and requirements that a company must adhere to in order to deploy innovative technologies. This could include compliance with industry-specific regulations, intellectual property rights, health and safety standards, etc.
 - *Regulatory Compliance:* This service assists companies in ensuring that their technologies and operations comply with local, national, and international regulations. This may involve navigating complex regulatory frameworks, obtaining necessary permits or licenses, and ensuring ongoing compliance with evolving laws.
 - *Access to New Solutions:* This involves helping companies identify and gain access to new technologies, products, or services that can enhance their operations or offerings. It may include scouting for innovative solutions in the market or facilitating partnerships with technology providers.
 - *Creating New Partnerships:* This service focuses on establishing collaborations and partnerships between or other businesses to foster innovation and mutual growth.
 - *Supporting Technological Development for Market Fit:* This involves providing guidance and assistance to companies in adapting and refining their technologies to meet market demands and consumer needs. It may include market research, product development strategies, and prototyping.
- **Unique Value Propositions:** description of the TL unique value proposition (e.g., accelerated development timelines for innovative hydrogen technologies, cost-effective access to infrastructure and expertise typically unavailable to startups and SMEs, etc.)

2.3.2 OITB Access to Services

Explain how the services will be delivered to the target customers. Description of the mechanism of access to the OITB through the SEP by open calls.

Companies will have access to the services after participating in an Open Call.

Open Calls will be organized with the aim of selecting the most promising technologies to be tested in the TLs. All criteria for evaluation of applications and further relevant information including user conditions will be compiled and transparently published on the project website. Effective measures to support applicants (e. g. a FAQ section) will be implemented. An evaluation panel will assess the applications with respect to their technical and economic performance.

The selection process is based on a set of criteria aimed at evaluating different areas of the companies and their technologies. Criteria will include the following:

- Business Model, Competition and Market Fit
- Team Maturity, Technical Skills, Market & Personal Skills and Recent Growth
- Alignment with consortium strategy and European Funds, new opportunities unlocking
- Relevance of the Solution, Tech, IP Protection, and Product Development Potential
- Consortium & investors synergy, Ability of Investors, and Government Environment

More specific details will be discussed during the Open Call preparation phase by all the project partners involved in the OITB.

2.3.3 Revenue Streams

2.3.3.1 Revenue Streams – TL level

Describe how the OITB will generate income from the TLs. The mechanism of income generation is described for each TL. Content covers all the possible income sources for each TL, including:

- **Pay-Per-Use Fees:** Charges for access to technical test lines based on usage duration or volume of services.
- **Service Fees:** Non-technical consulting or support services.
- **Revenue from By-Products:** Sale of hydrogen and/or any other valuable byproduct generated during tests (e.g. biogenic carbon dioxide).

2.3.3.2 Revenue Streams – SEP level

Each Test Line will contribute to the SEP's creation and management costs through a membership fee. This fee consists of a fixed portion for initial setup costs and a variable portion based on a percentage of Test Line-generated revenues. During the project's initial four years, consortium members can access OITB services free of charge. Selected startups and SMEs participating via Open Calls will pay fair and reasonable access fees to cover unfunded costs.

- **Membership Fees:** Description of the policy adopted by the SEP for the membership fee from consortium members or affiliated companies for continued access to the ecosystem.

2.3.4 Pricing Strategy

Detail the approach to pricing the services and the reasoning behind it. Content include:

- **Tiered Pricing:** Different price levels based on service type, usage duration, etc.
- **Subsidized Access:** Reduced rates for early-stage startups during the initial project phase, supported by EU funding.
- **Value-Based Pricing:** Pricing aligned with the high value offered (e.g., access to advanced facilities otherwise unaffordable for small companies).

2.3.5 Marketing Strategy and Sales Plan

This section describes the marketing strategy for the OITB. Define how the OITB will differentiate itself in the hydrogen production market and the methods to promote the OITB and attract target customers. Outline how the OITB will convert interest into committed customers.

Content include:

- **Positioning Statement and Key Differentiators:** positioning statement and key differentiators describing the distinct and unique value that sets H₂SHIFT apart from its competitors within the market of services for hydrogen production sector.
- **Marketing Strategies**
 - Digital Marketing:
 - Website, showcasing success stories.
 - Social media campaigns on LinkedIn, X/BlueSky, and industry-specific platforms.
 - Public Relations (PR):
 - Press releases to announce milestones and Open Calls.
 - Articles and interviews in industry publications and blogs.
 - Events and Conferences:
 - Participation in hydrogen and clean energy trade fairs.
 - Hosting webinars and workshops on hydrogen technology advancements.
 - Promotional Campaigns
- **Sales Strategy**
 - Sales Process:
 - Lead generation through industry events, partnerships, and digital campaigns, following the engagement strategy defined in ecosystem mapping (i.e. D2.2)
 - Initial consultation via SEP to understand customer needs and recommend services.
 - Contract negotiation and onboarding through clear, transparent agreements.
 - Sales Channels: direct outreach, referrals from partners, and inbound queries via the SEP.
 - Sales Team Structure:
 - Description of the sales team that manages the relationship with startups and SMEs.

2.3.6 Customer Acquisition Costs

Estimate the cost of acquiring new customers. Content include:

- **Breakdown of costs:**
 - Marketing expenses (advertising, PR, and events).
 - Sales expenses (team salaries and outreach tools).

2.3.7 Retention Strategies

Strategy to keep customers engaged. Content includes:

- **Ongoing Engagement:**
 - Personalized updates on new services, facilities, and industry trends.
 - Access to exclusive webinars or networking events for customers.
- **Customer Success Program:** A dedicated team to ensure customer satisfaction and support long-term partnerships.
- **Incentives:** Discounts for repeat customers or referral bonuses for introducing new clients.

2.4 Operations Plan and organizational structure of the TLs

This section describes in detail the technology requirements and the operative structure of the Test Lines of the OITB on the short- and long- term. The information included pertains the facilities and the personnel involved in providing the services, and how it is organized the workflow.

2.4.1 Facilities, Equipment, and Technology Requirements

Describes the current facilities and the upgrades required to meet the customers' needs. The summary of technical information about TLs and upgrade needs refers to the results of Task 3.4. (Test Line upgrade analysis – D3.4).

- **Current Facilities:**

A description of the current state of the facilities, including lab spaces, pilot plants, and specialized testing areas for hydrogen production technologies. The existing technical capacities (e.g., electrolysis equipment, storage systems, analytical tools) are specified.

- **Required Upgrades:**

Based on the Test Line upgrade analysis (Task 3.4), the improvements needed to meet the evolving customer demands (e.g. new electrolyzer auxiliaries to handle higher volumes, advanced sensors for precise data collection, software upgrades for automation and data analysis, etc.). Highlight how these upgrades will ensure scalability, reliability, and alignment with customer needs.

2.4.2 Organizational Information

Describes how each organization will manage the accesses to their infrastructure from the point of view of the personnel involved to support the customers of the TLs.

- **Team Composition:**

Provide numbers and roles of the key personnel involved in managing and operating the Test Lines:

- **Technical Staff:** Engineers, technicians, and researchers specialized in hydrogen technologies.
- **Support Staff:** Logistics, IT, and administrative personnel.
- **Leadership Roles:** Test Line managers, responsible for planning, execution, and customer interaction.

- **Responsibilities and Hierarchy:**

- Workflow management and task allocation.
- Quality assurance and compliance oversight.
- Coordination with the Single Entry Point (SEP) for customer onboarding and reporting.

2.4.3 Supply Chain Management

This section describes how each organization is managing its inventory and supply chain to ensure the operative availability of the infrastructure.

- **Inventory Management:**

- Procedures for maintaining an inventory of critical spare parts, consumables, and raw materials like catalysts, membranes, and chemicals.
- Just-in-time inventory practices to reduce costs while ensuring availability.

- **Supplier Relationships:**

- Collaborations with reliable vendors for specialized components.
- Contingency sourcing strategies to mitigate supply disruptions.

2.4.4 Operational Workflow

This section describes how each organization is managing the process of providing the services to the customers.

- **Service Delivery Process:**

- Steps for engaging with customers via the SEP, including initial consultations, test planning, execution, and feedback loops.
- General schedule with timeline and logistics for conducting tests, analyzing results, and delivering reports.

- **Quality Assurance:**
 - Monitoring standards for accuracy, reliability, and safety throughout the workflow.
- **Safety and security:**
 - Operational safety planning, including safety protocols applied and safety training requirements.
 - Security planning: protocols for IPR and confidentiality protection.
- **Logistics:**
 - Efficient scheduling to maximize facility usage and minimize downtime.

2.5 Financial Plan

This section describes in detail the financial plan of the Test Lines of the OITB on the short- and long- term.

2.5.1 Test Line Costs

- **Initial Investments:**
 - Specific financial needs for upgrading existing infrastructure, such as procurement of new equipment, facility renovations, and staff training.
- **Ongoing Maintenance:**
 - Recurring costs for maintaining and calibrating equipment, replacing consumables, and facility upkeep.

2.5.2 Revenue Projections

- **Access Fees (for each TL):**
Forecasted revenue from customer usage of technical and non-technical services.
- **By-Product Sales (for each TL):**
Additional income from selling hydrogen and biogenic carbon dioxide produced during tests (if applicable).
- **Membership Contributions (for the SEP):**
Anticipated income from regular membership fees paid by consortium members.

2.5.3 Expense Projections

- **Operational Costs (for each TL):**
Breakdown of material costs, personnel salaries, and facility utility bills.
- **Marketing and Outreach (for the SEP):**
Investments in promoting services to attract startups and SMEs.

2.5.4 Profit and Loss Statement

- A clear overview of expected revenues, costs, and profit margins.

2.5.5 Cash Flow Statement

- **Inflow Projections:**
Monthly or quarterly cash inflows from service usage, memberships, and by-product sales.
- **Outflow Projections:**
Costs for staff, materials, and maintenance, along with upgrade expenses.

2.5.6 Break-Even Analysis and Financial metrics

- **Break-Even Point:**

The point where total revenue equals total costs, allowing the OITB to sustain itself without external funding.

To complement the break-even analysis, other financial metrics will be estimated; for example, the Net Present Value (NPV) of the OITB will evaluate the project's profitability over its expected lifetime, considering the time value of money, discounting future cash inflows and outflows to present values

2.5.7 Funding Requirements and Use

- **Future Needs:**

Highlight areas requiring additional funding, such as advanced equipment or expanding service offerings.

- **Utilization Plan:**

A transparent breakdown of how new funds will be allocated to ensure investor confidence.

2.5.8 Business Model Canvas

All the financial information will be collected in a Business Model Canvas to wrap up. Simple infographic structures will be elaborated.

2.6 Risk Assessment

This section describes in detail the Risk assessment of the Test Lines of the OITB on the short- and long- term. This section will include the information elaborated in the D1.4 – Risk Management Plan of the project.

2.6.1 SWOT Analysis

- **Strengths:**

Highlight the strength points of the OITB (e.g., state-of-the-art research facilities, expert technical and non-technical teams, alignment of research trends of the TL with EU green energy policies, etc.)

- **Weaknesses:**

Highlight the weaknesses of the OITB (e.g., High initial setup costs, dependency on EU funding in the short term)

- **Opportunities:**

Highlight opportunities for growth and expansion of the OITB (e.g., growing demand for sustainable hydrogen solutions, potential partnerships with global energy leaders).

- **Threats:**

Highlight potential threats for the OITB (e.g., regulatory changes, competition from other test beds or independent service providers).

2.6.2 Risk Mitigation Strategies

Mitigation strategies at TL and SEP levels.

- **Financial Risks:**

For example, diversify revenue streams and secure long-term funding agreements.

- **Operational Risks:**

For example, implement robust maintenance schedules and backup equipment plans.

- **Market Risks:**

For example, continuous market research to stay ahead of trends and adjust services accordingly.

2.6.3 Contingency Plans

Define contingency plans at TL and SEP level.

- **Critical Operation Backup:**
Describe backup options to ensure TL operation (e.g., alternative suppliers for critical materials/components, redundant systems for key testing equipment).
- **Financial Resilience:**
Describe options at SEP and TL level to ensure financial resilience (e.g., establish a reserve fund to cover unexpected costs, develop a scalable model to adjust operations based on demand fluctuations).

3 Conclusions

The document provided a general structure proposed for the Business Plan of the OITB, together with the main information that the Business Plan will include.

1. OITB concept and objectives
2. Market analysis
3. Business Model and marketing strategy
4. Operations Plan and organizational structure of the TLs
5. Financial Plan
6. Risk Assessment

The final Business Plan and Strategy will be elaborated starting from this structure throughout the project and progressively updated when the required information will be available, to be released at the end of the project.